

THE EFFECT OF MATCHING GAME THERAPY ON THE MEMORY OF CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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Abstract

Introduction: Autism is a neurological developmental disorder characterized by limitations in social interaction, communication, and repetitive and restricted behaviors. Children with autism often experience cognitive impairments, including memory, which affect learning and daily adaptation. One of the interventions used to improve memory is game-based therapy, such as matching games, which can train children's concentration and memory. **Purpose:** This study aims to analyze the effect of matching game therapy on memory of children with autism. **Methods:** This study used a pre-experiment design with a one group pretest-posttest design approach on 20 respondents with autism. Sampling was done by purposive sampling technique. Memory was measured using the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Fourth Edition (WISC-IV) observation sheet. Data were analyzed using paired t test. **Result:** The results showed that there was an effect of matching game therapy on the memory of children with autism with a p value = 0.001 ($\alpha = 0.05$). **Conclusion:** This study concludes that matching game therapy has an effect on improving the memory of children with autism. The findings recommend the importance of using matching game therapy as an intervention to improve memory in children with autism.

Keywords: Autism, Memory, Matching Game Therapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Autism is a neurological developmental disorder characterised by limitations in social interaction, communication, and repetitive and restricted behaviours [1]. Children with autism often experience difficulties in cognitive aspects, one of which is memory, which affects learning abilities and daily adaptation functions [2]. Memory plays an important role in supporting academic and social success, so appropriate intervention methods are needed.

Globally, the prevalence of autism has shown a significant increase. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), one in 36 children in the United States will be identified with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) by 2023 [3]. In Indonesia, data on the prevalence of autism is still limited, but the Indonesian Ministry of Health estimates that there are around 2.4 million children with autism spectrum disorder, and only a small proportion receive appropriate and early intervention [4]. This highlights the urgency of developing accessible, engaging and effective interventions for children with autism.

One method used to help improve cognitive abilities, including memory in children with autism, is game-based therapy. This approach utilises play as a fun and structured learning tool. One form of educational game that is widely applied is matching game, which is a game of matching pictures, words, or symbols to train concentration, memory and other thinking skills [5]. This matching activity stimulates children's ability to remember patterns and improve the process of working memory and long-term memory [6].

Research conducted by Siska & Indaryani (2019), showed that the use of interactive media, including matching games, can improve focus, attention, and memory in children with special needs, including children with autism. In addition, this kind of game is also considered more interesting so that it can reduce pressure in the learning process, as well as increase children's motivation to be involved [7].

However, preliminary studies conducted at SLB Rajawali Makassar showed that the memory ability of children with autism at the school was not optimal. Based on interviews with teachers, it was found that the matching game intervention has never been used specifically, and the existing learning media is still limited to general puzzles. This finding indicates a gap in the application of more innovative and adaptive cognitive learning strategies for children with autism.

This research integrates the matching game approach as a form of intervention that has never been implemented in SLB Rajawali Makassar. The main focus of this study is to evaluate the impact of the intervention on improving memory skills in children with autism. In the context of limited access to contextualised and fun cognitive interventions in special schools, this study is expected to contribute to the development of game-based educational therapies that are effective, measurable, and appropriate to the needs of children with autism in Indonesia.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study used a pre-experiment design with a one group pretest-posttest design approach, conducted in February 2024 at SLB Rajawali Makassar. The population was all 30 children with autism. Samples were taken using purposive sampling technique, with inclusion criteria: children were cooperative and participated in the matching game therapy session until completion; exclusion criteria: children were not present during the study. There were 20 children who fulfilled the inclusion criteria.

The instrument used was the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Fourth Edition (WISC-IV) observation sheet, including digit forward and digit backward. Digit forward assesses the ability to remember and repeat numbers in sequence, while digit backward assesses the ability to remember and repeat numbers in reverse, each within 30 seconds. Assessment is done by ticking (√) on the correct answer. Interpretation of the results, if the score is 17-19 (very superior)= very high memory, score 15-16 (superior)= memory above the average of children of the same age, score 13-14 (above average)= strong memory, score 8-12 (average)= good memory, score 6-7 (below average)= weak memory, score 4-5 (borderline)= limited memory, score 1-3 (low score)= impaired memory. Data were analysed using paired t-test with a significance level of 5% ($p < 0.05$). This study has received ethical approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Makassar Poltekkes Kemenkes (No: 0207/M/KEPK-PTKMS/III/2024).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Frequency distribution of respondent characteristics

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
7-12 year	10	50.0
13-15 year	4	20.0
16-18 year	6	30.0
Gender		
Male	15	75.0
Female	5	25.0
Education		
Elementary	12	60.0
Junior high school	5	5.0
Senior high school	3	15.0
Total	20	100

Based on Table 1 of 20 children with autism who became respondents, the age distribution showed that most respondents were in the age range of 7-12 years as many as 10 people (50%), followed by 16-18 years of age as many as 6 people (30%), and the remaining 13-15 years as many as 4 people (20%). This finding shows that the majority of children with autism in the study were in elementary school age to early adolescence. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2020), a diagnosis of autism is generally made before the age of 8 years, so interventions at the age of 7-12 years are crucial in supporting their cognitive and social

development [8]. Based on gender, the majority of respondents were male, as many as 15 people (75%), while only 5 respondents (25%) were female. This result is in line with the global prevalence of autism, which is more prevalent in men than women [2,9]. Loomes (2017) in his study mentioned this prevalence is related to biological, genetic, and neuroanatomical factors, where men have a higher susceptibility to neurological developmental disorders such as autism [10]. In terms of education level, most children had primary school education as many as 12 respondents (60%), followed by junior high school as many as 5 people (25%), and senior high school as many as 3 people (15%). This reflects the age characteristics of the respondents, which are mostly at the age of primary education. Formal education for children with autism plays an important role in improving academic, social and communication skills [11]. However, challenges in the learning process remain, hence the need for adaptive learning methods and therapy-based interventions, such as game-based therapy, to support their cognitive development. [12]

3.2. Normality test

Table 2. Normality test analysis

	Statistic	N	Sig.	Statistic	N	Sig.
Pre-test	,118	20	200a	,955	20	,442
Post-test	,146	20	200a	,943	20	,270

Based on table 2 above, the results of the normality test with the number $n \leq 50$, the results of the normality test read in shapiro-wilk obtained a value in the pre-test intervention group significance value (sig.) 0.442 ($p > 0.05$). In the post-test intervention group, the significance value (sig.) 0.270 ($p > 0.05$). So it is concluded that the research data is normally distributed, therefore the researcher uses a paired t test to analyze the effect of matching game therapy on the memory of children with autism.

3.3. Analysis of the Effect of Matching Game Therapy on the Memory of Children With Autism

Table 3. The results of the analysis of the effect of matching game therapy on the memory of children with autism

Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	ρ
Pre Test	20	5,45	5,50	3,804	0,001
Post Test	20	6,60	6,00	3,926	

Based on table 3, there is a difference in the memory value of autistic children before and after being given matching game therapy. The mean memory score before the intervention was 5.45 with a median of 5.50 and a standard deviation (SD) of 3.804. After the intervention, the mean increased to 6.60 with a median of 6.00 and a standard deviation (SD) of 3.926. Analysis using paired t-test showed a value of $p=0.001$ ($\alpha = 0.05$). This p value < 0.05 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference between the memory of children with autism before and after being given matching game therapy. This finding indicates that the intervention was effective in improving memory in the group of autistic children. The results showed an increase in the mean from 5.4 to 6.60, indicating a significant increase, although numerically relatively small but proven to be statistically significant. This finding is in line with previous research showing that intervention through interactive games is effective in improving cognitive abilities, including working memory, in children with special needs [13]. Matching activities in matching games are believed to stimulate short-term memory processing and visual memory in children with autism, thus contributing to their memory improvement. [6]

However, the high standard deviation values in the pre-test (3.804) and post-test (3.926) indicate that there is a considerable difference in memory ability between individuals. This indicates that not all children experienced the same improvement in memory after the intervention. This variation is common in the population of children with autism, as their cognitive profiles are highly heterogeneous [13]. Several factors such as age, severity of autism, level of focus, and motivation of the child may influence the success of this therapy. [14,15]

4. CONCLUSION

This study shows that matching game therapy has a significant effect on improving the memory of children with autism. Matching game therapy can be an alternative cognitive intervention that is effective in supporting the memory ability of children with autism. However, considerable individual variations indicate the need to adjust the therapy approach according to the characteristics of each child to optimize the intervention results.

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